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Review Article

A Review On 'Mukul Myrrh Tree' Formulations Used in Ayurveda "(Guggulu)"

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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda, Guggulu is the best among herbs that are used for Medoroga and Vata disorders. It is widely used for obesity and it is also known as fat burning agent all over the world. It helps to lower cholesterol and triglycerides level. Guggulu is very effective in rheumatoid arthritis, gout and sciatica. It is also one of the most important Rasayana of Ayurveda. It has been used extensively by Ayurvedic physicians for centuries to treat a wide variety of disorders, besides its use in pharmaceutical and perfumery industries. Guggulu is a gum or resin extracted from the plant *Commiphora wightii* (Arn.) Bhand. (Syn. *Commiphora mukulHook. ex. Stocks*) or Guggulu tree. Guggulu is a shrub or small tree belonging to *Burseraceae* family. Guggulu contains volatile oil, gum resin, guggulipids, guggulsterones, guggulsterols, mukolol and other steroids. Guggulu is very much used in Ayurvedic system of medicine as astringent, anti-septic, expectorant, aphrodisiac, carminative, anti spasmodic, emmenagogue. Basically it is used almost in every kind of illness due to its amazing treating power. This review is an attempt to describe the Pharmacological activities of Guggulu and variable uses of Guggulu in several diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Guggulu (*Commiphora mukul*) means "fights against disease", is an indigenous well known drug and has been used for centuries to treat several ailments. Guggulu is an oleo-gum resin that exudes spontaneously as a result of injury from the bark of *Commiphora mukul*. It is a key

ingredient of a large number of Ayurvedic formulations. Hence, it is considered as one of the "Divyaushadhis" in Ayurveda. Guggulu was introduced as a medicine in 1966, and but approved as a hypo-lipidemic drug for marketing in India In 1986. Shutiestela produce in number farosis, accities like Anti-inflammatory, Anti-

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obesity, Anti-neoplastic, Anti-diabetic, Hypo-lipidemic, Anti-arthritic, Anti-fertility, Anti-Atherosclerotic etc.

The Guggulu plant may be Found from northern Africa to central Asia, but is Most common in Northern India. It prefers arid And semi-arid climates and is tolerant of poor soil. It is a shrub or small tree, reaching a maximum Height of 3m, with thin papery bark. Guggulu Produces a resinous sap known as gum Guggulu. Guggulu is a natural health Product used primarily to reduce elevated blood Cholesterol levels. It has been used for many years As a hypocholesterolaemic agent in India. Guggulu Is one of the best rewarding herbs for Vata Diseases. Various preparations of Guggulu used in. Sciatica, hemiplegia, gout, rheumatic diseases, Facial paralysis etc. Guggulu is beneficial in Cleansing and healing of wounds and to reduce Oedema due to its anti-inflammatory and antiseptic properties. In digestive ailments also like Anorexia, flatulence, worm infestations, piles etc,

Vernacular Names

Table 1: Showing vernacular names of Guggulu

Bengal - Gugal, Guggul, Mukul, Ranghanturb

Sanskrit- Bhavabhishta, Bhutahara, Devadhupa,

Deveshta, Dhurta, Divya, Durga, Guggulu,

Jatala, Jatayu, Kalaniriyasa, Kaushika

Gujarat - Gugal, Gugali, Gugar, Guggul, Ranghanturb

Hindi - Gogil, Gugal, Guggul, Mukul, Ranghanturb

Marathi - Guggala, Gulag, Mukul

Tamil- Gukkal, Gukkulu, Maishakshi

Telugu - Gugul, Mahisaksh, Maisakshi.

History

➤ In Vedas – Specifically in Atharva Veda, it is mentioned that Yakshma and other diseases will not spread to the area fumigated by Guggulu and introduced as well known DHUPAN DRAVYA.

➤ In Samhitas – It is observed that the internal usage of Guggulu was increased during Samhita period.

➤ Charak samhita – Maharishi Charaka has described Guggulu as the best drug for MEDOROGA and VATA SAMAKA.

• And also recommended the drug in Rasayana Chikitsa where Shilajeet and Guggulu were used with cow milk.

• The drug also has been described by him in other diseases as highly effective medicine like Kustha, Bhagandara, Indralupta, Kitibha, Arsha, Apchi, Pama And Sweta Pradara.

➤ Sushruta Samhita - Maharishi Sushruta has described Guggulu in the list of seven most important drugs for the treatment of Sthaulya.

➤ Acharya Sushruta has prescribed Guggulu with cow urine in condition of vitiated Vata with Medodhatu dominated by Kapha dosha.

➤ This drug is also mentioned as highly effective in the treatment of Hrdroga , Aruchi, Gulma and Antarvidradhi. He also documented that the new guggulu is VRSHYA while old guggulu is

➤ **Apakarsana-**

Ashtang Hridya - Vagbhata has described it a drugs of choice in Medoroga for its lipid lowering action. He has also used the drug in Snehavyapada and in diseases produced due to vitiated Medodhatu, Kapha, Vata and in Amavata.

➤ Sharngdhara Samhita - He quoted it among the drugs to be used for Rasayan Karma.

In Nighantus -

➤ Dhanwantari nighantu - included it under "Chandanadi Varga".

➤ Madanpala Nighantu - included it under "Karpooradi Varga".

➤ Kaiydev Nighantu - has mentioned it under "Aushadi Varga".

➤ Bhavprakash Nighantu - has described it in "Karpooradi Varga".

➤ Raj Nighantu - included it under "Chandanadi Varga".

➤ Mahaushadi Nighantu - included it under "Chandanadi Varga".

➤ Shaligram Nighantu has mentioned it under "Karpooradi Verga".

Guggulu

Family: Burseraceae

It is a slow growing, highly branched, spiny shrub or a small tree with crooked branches ending in sharp spines. It is a desert plant adjusted to grow in difficult soil and moisture conditions. The plant remains leafless during winter season that is from October to March. New leaves sprout during April, are short lived and do not fall until September. A short spell of rainfall initiates leaf formation. Guggal, an oleo-gum resin of pale brown or dull green color, exuds from bark during winter season.

Common Names:

- English: - Myrrh
- Sanskrit: - Guggulu
- Kannada: - Guggul
- Hindi: - Guggal

Distribution:

Guggal in a xerophytes and grow naturally in and rocky zones of India... i.e Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh and also in Pakistan.

Agroclimatic Requirements:

The plant grows very well in warm dry climatic and heme suitable dry regions. Sandy or sandy loam soils are best for cultivation. The plant susceptible to frost hence such situation to be avoided.

Cultivation:

It can be propagated by seeds and vegetatively through stem cuttings. The seed germination is erratic and also very poor (5%) due to the presence of hard seed coat. The seeds are mechanically scarified with sand paper and are kept under running water for 24hr, seedlings may be raised in polythene bags and are planted in the main field. Semi-hardwood cuttings of about 15-20cm length are taken and planted in well prepared nursery beds. The beds are irrigated lightly after planting and regularly thereafter. 10-12 months old seedlings are to be planted in the main filled.

Inputs:

Sr. No	Materials	Per acre	Per hectare
1	No. of plants	1000	2500
2	Farm Yard Manure (t)	10	25
	Fertilizers	—	—

Planting:

Land is prepared well in advance of rainy seasons by 2-3 ploughings and make field into plots of convenient size. Dig the plots of size 0.5x 0.5 x 0.5 m (0.5 cm³) with a spacing of 3x3m. Pits are filled with FYM and top soil. The rooted cutting is planted in the pits during the raining season. As the plant grows, they are trained properly by cutting the side branches.

Irrigation and Interculture:

Light irrigation during the summer season is required for good growth of plants. One weeding and one hoeing is needed in carly growth of the crop. But the soil is stirred up around the plants (bushes) two times per year.

Harvesting:

The plant should be allowed to grow for at least five to six years before commencing incision of thick branches for extracting oleo-gum resin. The oleo-gum resin is tapped during winter, from November - February, by making a 7-10 cm long incision in the main stem near the base. The cut part is completely covered with resin in about a month's time. The exuded gum secreted is collected every week up to one month after which further exudation of gum stops.

Yield: from 10-year-old plant, about 700-900 g of gum resin may be obtained. This intrun may give an yield of about 700-900 kg of gum resign per hectare.

Chemical Constituents

In its chemical composition volatile oil, resins, gum and a bitter compound is found. Five types of guggul sterols, Z-guggul sterne, E- guggulsterone, guggul sterol - I, II, III, sesamine, cholesterol, mucolol and other steroids are also found. Monocyclic diterpenes-alpha - camphorene and cembrene isolated from resin; allylcembrol isolated from plant and characterized (Chem-Abstr. 1972,77, 111554 t). Three new steroids - guggulsterols I,II,III are isolated from gum resin (Tetrahedron 1972,28, 2341). Cembrene A isolated from resin and characterized (Tetrahedron 1973, 29, 341). Isolation and structure elucidation of two aliphatic tetrols octadecan - 1, 2, 3, 4 and eicosan - 1, 2, 3, 4 - tetrol from gum resin (Tetrahedron 1973, 29, 1595). Guggulsterol VI and Z - guggulsterol isolated from gum resin (Tetrahedron 1982, 38, 2949).

Macroscopic and Microscopic Features

- 1) Macroscopic** Drug occurs in vermicular pieces of pale yellow or brown coloured mass, makes milky emulsion in hot water and readily burns, when fresh viscid and golden coloured, odour ;aromatic, taste is bitter and astringent.
- 2) Microscopic** Foreign matter Not more than 4 %; Total Ash Not more than 5 %; Acid-insoluble ash Not more than 1%; Alcohol-soluble extractive Not less than 27 %; Water-soluble extractive Not less than 53%; Volatile oil Not less than 1%.

Botanical Discrimination

- Woody shrub or a small tree
- Grows to the height of 2-3 meter

- Much branched with characteristics silvery and paper like bark peelings.
- Branches are knotty and crooked, divaricate, usually ending in a sharp spine.

- Leaves: The leaves are rhomboid-ovate, 1-3 foliate, serrate-toothed in the upper part, smooth and shining, the lateral leaflets when present less than half the size of the terminal ones.

- Flowers: Flowers in the fascicles of 2-3; pedicels very short. Calyx campanulate, glandular, hairy; lobes are 4-5 in number, triangular, as long as the tube. Petals are brownish red, broadly linear, nearly thrice the length of the calyx, reflexed at the apex. Stamens are 8-10 in number, alternatively long and short, half the length of the petals. Ovary oblong-ovoid, attenuated into the style.

- Gum Resin: Pale yellow to brown aromatic gum resin obtained from the bark of the plant. Agglomerated tears of resin are somewhat transparent, with waxy surface and brittle in nature. Gum-resin is thick, scented, burnt on fire, liquifies in sun heat. When dissolved in water, it turns milky white.

Varieties Of Guggulu

➤ Bhavmishra described five varieties of Guggulu –

1. Mahishaksha - Mahishaksha has the colour of honey-bee or Anjana (antimony sulphide).

2. Mahanila is similar to its name and looks like a Sapphire, a precious stone.

Extremely blue in colour

3. Kumuda - Kumuda resembles Kumuda flower (white) in colour.

4. Padma - Padma resembles Manikya (ruby red).

5. Hiranya (Kanaka) - Hiranya is like gold in colour.

Mahikshaksh and Mahanila varieties are beneficial to elephants, Kumuda and Padma bestow health to horses, Hiranya variety is best suited for humans.

➤ Generally, main two types of Guggulu are available :-

1. Kana guggulu

2. Bhainsa guggulu

Kana guggulu –

1. Found in Marwar.

2. Colour – Raktabh peeta

• Bhainsa guggulu –

1. Found in Kutch and Sindh.

2. Colour – Haritabh peeta

➤ Other two varieties of Guggulu has mentioned in the texts books of Ayurveda:

1) Nava Guggulu

2) Purana Guggulu

• The freshly collected Guggulu is tissue builder and aphrodisiac and if stored for more than one year, it is a depletory of tissues. The characters of fresh one are, it is oily, yellowish looks like a ripen Jambu fruit, fragrant and gummy in nature.

• Purana or old decayed Guggulu is dry, emitting bad smell, devoid of natural colour and potency.

• Nava Guggulu is useful in debility, whereas the old variety - Purana Guggulu is salutary in obesity and diabetes.

○ Note - Guggulu older than 5 years is considered as Purana Guggulu.

	Nava (Fresh) Guggulu	Purana (Old) Guggulu
Verna (Colour)	Kanchana Sankasha (Bright Yellow) or pakva jambu phala sadrusha (Dark brown)	Tyakta prakurti (yellowish brown)
Gandha (odour)	Sugandha (pleasant)	Durgandha (offensive)
Guna (qualities)	Snigdha (oily/greasy), picchila (slimy)	Laghu (lighter), ruksha (rough), tikshna, Vishad (clean), sukshma, sara
Karma (actions)	Bruhana, Vrushya, Rasayana, Kamottejaka and Artavajanana	Lekhana, Medohara and shukranashana

Adulterants

- There are many adulterants used in gum resin of *Commiphora mukul* for commercial purpose.
- The Indian adulterants commonly used are gum resin of *Boswellia serrata* and *Hymenictyon excelsum* but out of both, *Boswellia serrate* (*Salai guggulu*) is major adulterant.
- The colour and smell of both the gum resins after solidification almost resemble each other, since both the plants belong to the same family *Burseraceae*.
- Gum resin of *Boswellia serrate* is distinguished by its yellowish green, golden or milky tears, seldom amalgamated into lumps and a characteristic terpentine like odour.

A. *Commiphora* (Guggul)

Purification Of Guggulu

- **Need of Guggulu Shodhana** - As Guggulu is an exudate, external impurities in the form of dust, dry leaves and other foreign materials are accepted in Guggulu. After purification, the herb becomes safer and more effective for use.
- Traditionally Guggulu is purified in *Triphala kvatha* for 12 hours (in *Dola Yantra*) and then fried with ghee before administered internally.
- According to *Nighantu Ratanakar* decoctions of *Guduchi*, *Triphala*, *Vasa* and *Cow's milk* are to be used for purification.

Pharmacology Actions

a) Anti – inflammatory and Anti – arthritic activity: -

- Oleo – resin was found to be highly potent anti – inflammatory agent, as compared to hydrocortisone and buta – zoladin against Brownlee’s formaldehyde – induced arthritis in albino rats.
- Oleo – resin fraction possessed significant anti – arthritic and anti – inflammatory activities, the minimum effective dose being 12.5mg/100g body weigh.
- In arthritis, the extract suppress the activation of inflammatory cytokine and lowers the inflammation. It’s also suppresses the activation of interleukins and prostaglandins, and is compared to be more effective then betamethasone.

b) Anti-atherosclerotic activity: -

- Effect of gum was observed on serum cholesterol, fibrino – lytic activity and platelet adhesive index in healthy individuals (group 1) and in patient of Cad (group 2) for a period of 30 days.
- Serum fibrino – lytic activity improved by 22% and 19% at the end of 24 hrs, as after 30 days it was 40% and 30% in group 1 & 2 respectively.

- Platelet adhesive index showed 22% and 19% after 30 days in group 1 and group 2 respectively.

c) Anti-obesity activity :-

- Crude Guggulu was found to reduce the body weight of hydrogenated ground – nut oil treated rabbits.
- Preliminary clinical trials on 22 patients of hypercholestrolaemia associated with obesity, IHD, HTN, DM etc.
- Guggulu crude was administrated orally (6.12mg) in three divided doses for 15 days to one month.
- A fall in total serum cholesterol and serum lipid – phosphorus was found in all the cases treated with Guggulu.
- The body weight of 10 patients also found to be reduced significantly.

d) Hypo – lipidemic activity:-

- Typical Guggul – lipid preparation contain 2.5-5% of the plant sterols Guggulsterone E and Z.
- These two components have been reported to exert effects on lipids. To evaluate the effects of Guggul on disorders of lipid metabolism, with special reference to atherosclerosis and obesity,

Satyavati et al. Conducted the first animal study on rabbits, from 1964-1966.

- It was demonstrated that administration of gum Guggul significantly lowered the serum cholesterol levels of hyperlipidemic rabbits, prevented cholesterol – induced arteriosclerosis and decreased the body weight of the animals.

e) Cardio – protective effects :-

- Several studies have reported the cardio – protective activity of Guggulsterone that showed the reversal of iso-proterenol induced cardiac damage and the associated metabolic changes and protects heart during low blood supply in rats.

f) Neuro protective effect :-

- Guggulipid reversed strepto-zotocin drug induced neuronal damage and memory deficits.
- In parallel with these reversals, levels of glutathione in the brains of Guggulipid – treated mice were significantly increased, suggesting that Guggulipid inhibits oxidative stress in the brain.
- Guggulipid has an antioxidant and anti-acetylcholine esterase activities; showed protective effect against strepto – zotocin induced memory deficits in the model of dementia.
- These observations suggest Guggulipid as a potential anti-dementia drug and cognitive enhancer.

g) Anti-bacterial activities :-

- It has been reported that the essential oil, chloroform extract and seven sesquiterpenoid compounds from the Oleo-gum-resin of Commiphora mukul showed the inhibitory action against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. And hence, is effectively used as traditional antibiotics for treating acne.

h) Thyroid-Stimulatory effect :-

- Several studies have shown that Guggulsterone stimulates the thyroid gland.

- Administration of Guggulsterone restored thyroid activity like an increase in iodine uptake by the thyroid and enhanced the activities of thyroid peroxidase and protease (thyroid enzyme) as well as oxygen consumption in hypothyroid rats.

i) Anti – Acne effect :-

- Guggulipid has been reported to be effective in the treatment of Nodulo-cystic acne.
- Patient with Nodulo-cystic acne had shown progressive reduction in lesions when received Guggulipid for 3 months and patients with oily faces, the acne responded better to Guggulipid.

j) Antioxidant effects :-

- Commiphora mukul extracts have been reported to possess antioxidant properties by inhibits the production of oxygen free radicals and prevents several tissues from damage. It is helpful for oxidative stress associated disease such as heart and nerve damage.

k) Anti-cancer Activities: -

- Guggulsterone has been shown to suppress proliferation, invasion, angiogenesis and metastasis of tumour cells.
- Various mechanisms have been suggested to explain the anti-carcinogenic effects of Guggulsterone, including suppression of inflammation and inhibition of nuclear receptors, transcription factors, inflammatory cytokines, apoptotic proteins and cell cycle-related proteins.
- Proliferation: Guggulsterone suppresses the growth and proliferation of a wide variety of tumor cells, including leukemia, head and neck carcinoma, multiple myeloma, lung carcinoma, breast carcinoma and ovarian carcinoma.

CONCLUSION

Guggulu is a multi-purpose drug and because of its magical properties, it is very beneficial in so many diseases. Guggulu has several uses which are supported by various researches done by researchers throughout the world. These findings could open a new window on the use of this plant in Ayurveda. Also, this plant is listed in IUCN list and thus rationale usage of the plant is the need of the hour so that we do not end up depleting this wonder drug of high therapeutic importance. Keeping this in view, stem, bark, and leaf of this plant should receive more attention so that the complete depletion on account of plant death due to tapping can be checked. This plant still possesses an unexplored potential and expansion of research materials would provide more opportunities for the discovery of novel bioactive principles from this plant. These conclusions could open a new window on the use of this plant in Ayurveda. This review clearly authenticates the Sanskrit definition of the term "guggul" which means one that protects against diseases. It is superbly reflected and proved by the diverse medicinal uses of this Ayurvedic drug.

REFERENCES

1. Carak Samhita, Agnivesa, Text with English translation and critical exposition based on Cakrapani Datta's Ayurveda Dipika, Sharma RK, Dash B, Chikitsasthanam, Rasayanadhyaya, P.5556, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series office, Varanasi 1966.
2. Bhardwaj, M., & Alia, A. (2019). Commiphora wightii (Arn.) Bhandari. Review of its botany, medicinal uses, pharmacological activities and phytochemistry. Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics, 9(4-s), 613-621.
3. Nohr, L. A., Rasmussen, L. B., & Straand, J. (2009). Resin from the mukul myrrh tree, guggul, can it be used for treating hypercholesterolemia? A randomized, controlled study. Complementary Therapies in Medicine, 17(1), 16-22.
4. Cunningham, A. B., Brinckmann, J. A., Kulloli, R. N., & Schippmann, U. (2018). Rising trade, declining stocks: The global gugal (Commiphora wightii) trade. Journal of ethnopharmacology, 223, 22-32.
5. Srivastava, S. (2024). Guggul: Potency and Mechanistic Insight for Tremendous Therapeutic Benefit. Current Traditional Medicine, 10(3), 75-83.
6. Garang, Z., Feng, Q., Luo, R., La, M., Zhang, J., Wu, L., ... & Jiangyong, S. (2023). Commiphora mukul (Hook. Ex Stocks) Engl.: Historical records, application rules, phytochemistry, pharmacology, clinical research, and adverse reaction. Journal of Ethnopharmacology, 317, 116717.
7. Halles JS. A drug for all seasons. Medical and Pharmacological history of aloe. Bull N Y Acad Med. 1990;66(6):647-59.
8. Yang, Y., Sun, X., Peng, C., Wei, J., & Yang, X. (2024). The Genus Commiphora: An Overview of Its Traditional Uses, Phytochemistry, Pharmacology, and Quality Control. Pharmaceuticals, 17(11), 1524.
9. Agarwal OP. Prevention of atheromatous 88Heart disease. Angiology. 1985;36(8):485-92.
10. Gajjar, U. H., & Pundrikakshudhu, K. (2022). Effect of shodhana (purification process) on guggulsterone E and Z in Commiphora mukul. JPC–Journal of Planar Chromatography–Modern TLC, 35(1), 13-21.
11. Aggarwal, K., & Singh, D. (2019). Commiphora mukul. Holistic Healthcare: Possibilities and Challenges Volume 2, 173.
12. Sarup, P., Pahuja, S., & Malik, J. (2022). Chemistry, biological activities, and uses of oleo-gum resin of Commiphora wightii. In Gums, Resins and Latexes of Plant Origin: Chemistry, Biological Activities and Uses (pp. 447-478). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

13. Hayes SM. Lichen planus—report of successful treatment with aloe vera. *Gen Dent*. May- 1999;47(3):268-72
14. Singh, A., Boregowda, S. S., Moin, A., Abu Lila, A. S., Aldawsari, M. F., Khafagy, E. S., ... & Jayaramu, R. A. (2022). Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Commiphora mukul* extract: evaluation of anti-arthritic activity in adjuvant-induced arthritis rat model. *Pharmaceutics*, 14(11), 2318.
15. Ahmad, M. A., Mujeeb, M., Akhtar, M., Khushtar, M., Arif, M., & Haque, M. R. (2020). Guggulipid: a promising multi-purpose herbal medicinal agent. *Drug research*, 70(04), 123-130.
16. Ni Y, Turner D, Yates KM, Tizard I. Isolation. And characterization of structural components Of Aloe vera L. leaf pulp. *Int Immunopharmacol*. 2004;4(14):1745-55
17. Akhter, G., & Javed, G. (2023). Recent Developments in Natural Compounds of Guggul and Production of Plant Material for Conservation and Pharmaceutical Demand *Commiphora wightii* (Arn.) Bhandari. *Plants for Immunity and Conservation Strategies*, 239-258.
18. S. Nityanand, J. S. Srivastava, and O. P. Asthana, "Clinical trials With guggulipid—a new hypolipidaemic agent," *The Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 323–328, 1989.
19. Latha, S., Selvamani, P., & Prabha, T. (2021). Pharmacological uses of the plants belonging to the genus *Commiphora*. *Cardiovascular & Hematological Agents in Medicinal Chemistry (Formerly)*, 19(2), 101-117.
20. AGGARWAL, K., & SINGH, D. (2019). *Commiphora mukul*. *Holistic Healthcare: Possibilities and Challenges Volume 2*, 173.
21. Ghritlahare, S. K., Satapathy, T., Panda, P. K., & Mishra, G. (2017). Ethnopharmacological story of guggul sterones: an overview. *Research Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 9(3), 182-188.
22. Khare, B., & Shukla, T. P. (2022). A review on polyherbal formulation used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research*, 13(01), 31-42.
23. Malik, J., & Mandal, S. C. (2024). *Commiphora spp.(Guggul): A Wonder Ayurvedic Drug*. In *Advances in Medicinal and Aromatic Plants* (pp. vol1-261). Apple Academic Press.
24. Sultan, K., Perveen, S., Zafar, S., Parveen, A., Iqbal, N., & AL-Huqail, A. A. (2023). Guggul. In *Essentials of Medicinal and Aromatic Crops* (pp. 573-601). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
25. S. Panda and A. Kar, "Gugulu (*Commiphora mukul*) induces Triiodothyronine production: possible involvement of lipid Peroxidation," *Life Sciences*, vol. 65, no. 12, pp. 137–141, 1999.
26. Cunningham, A. B., Brinckmann, J. A., Kulloli, R. N., & Schippmann, U. (2018). Rising trade, declining stocks: The global gugal (*Commiphora wightii*) trade. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 223, 22-32.
27. Sunita, S., Kalsi, V., Mukhtar, H. M., & Dubey, S. (2023, September). Medicinal properties and health benefits of guggul-*Commiphora mukul*. In *AIP conference proceedings* (Vol. 2800, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
28. Tomar, R., Kaur, G., Sannd, R., Singh, H., & Sarkar, B. (2014). A review on guggulu formulations used in Ayurveda. *Annals Ayurvedic Med*, 3, 96-113.
29. Kunnumakkara, A. B., Banik, K., Bordoloi, D., Harsha, C., Sailo, B. L., Padmavathi, G., ... & Aggarwal, B. B. (2018). Googling the Guggul (*Commiphora* and *Boswellia*) for prevention of chronic diseases. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 9, 686.

30. Blomquist, S. A., & Fernandez, M. L. (2024). Chios Mastic Gum: A Promising Phytotherapeutic for Cardiometabolic Health. *Nutrients*, 16(17), 2941.
31. Kumar, N., Sharma, N., Khera, R., Gupta, R., & Mehan, S. (2021). Guggulsterone ameliorates ethidium bromide-induced experimental model of multiple sclerosis via restoration of behavioral, molecular, neurochemical and morphological alterations in rat brain. *Metabolic brain disease*, 36, 911-925.
32. Bhat, M. H., Fayaz, M., Kumar, A., & Jain, A. K. (2019). Chemistry and pharmacology of Guggulsterone: An active principle of Guggul plant. *Plant and Human Health, Volume 3: Pharmacology and Therapeutic Uses*, 301-319.
33. Kumar, V., Singh, S., & Singh, R. (2020). Phytochemical constituents of guggul and their biological qualities. *Mini-Reviews in Organic Chemistry*, 17(3), 277-288.
34. Chando, A. D., Basudkar, V., Gharat, S., Momin, M., & Khan, T. (2023). Quantitative Estimation Of 6-Gingerol, E-Guggulsterone And Z-Guggulsterone In A Fixed Dose Combination Nanoemulgel By Rp-HPLC. *Indian Drugs*, 60(7).
35. Stancioiu, F., Bogdan, R., & Dumitrescu, R. (2023). Neuron-specific enolase (NSE) as a biomarker for autistic spectrum disease (ASD). *Life*, 13(8), 1736.
36. Khera, R., Mehan, S., Bhalla, S., Kumar, S., Alshammari, A., Alharbi, M., & Sadhu, S. S. (2022). Guggulsterone mediated JAK/STAT and PPAR-gamma modulation prevents neurobehavioral and neurochemical abnormalities in propionic acid-induced experimental model of autism. *Molecules*, 27(3), 889.
37. Dembitsky, V. M. (2024). Chemical Diversity of Ketosteroids as Potential Therapeutic Agents. *Microbiology Research*, 15(3), 1516-1575.
38. Batiha, G. E. S., Wasef, L., Teibo, J. O., Shaheen, H. M., Zakariya, A. M., Akinfe, O. A., ... & Papadakis, M. (2023). Commiphora myrrh: a phytochemical and pharmacological update. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's archives of pharmacology*, 396(3), 405-420.
39. Rawat, N., Mitra, S., Sharma, U., & Sharma, K. C. (2023). An overview of triphala guggulu and its ingredients. *Ayushdhara*, 10(1), 47-59.
40. Chauhan, A., Jindal, T., Chauhan, A., & Jindal, T. (2020). Biochemical and molecular methods for bacterial identification. *Microbiological methods for environment, food and pharmaceutical analysis*, 425-468.
41. Goyal, P., Chauhan, A., & Kaushik, P. (2010). Assessment of Commiphora wightii (Arn.) Bhandari (Guggul) as potential source for antibacterial agent. *Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 1(3), 71-75.
42. Aggarwal, G., Sharma, M., Singh, R., & Sharma, U. (2024). Ethnopharmacologically important highly subsidized Indian medicinal plants: Systematic review on their traditional uses, phytochemistry, pharmacology, quality control, conservation status and future prospective. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 320, 117385.
43. Srivastava, V., Mathur, D., Rout, S., Mishra, B. K., Pannu, V., & Anand, A. (2022). Ayurvedic herbal therapies: A review of treatment and management of dementia. *Current Alzheimer Research*, 19(8), 568-584.
44. Bhardwaj, M., & Alia, A. (2019). Commiphora wightii (Arn.) Bhandari. Review of its botany, medicinal uses, pharmacological activities and phytochemistry. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 9(4-s), 613-621.
45. Batool, S. A., Ghazanfar, E., Ahmed, H., Hussain, R., Azeem, M., Rasheed, M. M., ... & Atiq-ur-Rehman, M. (2025). Improved

- physicochemical properties of structurally modified titanium coated with zein–mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles–*Commiphora wightii* for orthopaedic applications. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 140870.
46. Nille, G. C., & Chaudhary, A. K. (2021). Potential implications of Ayurveda in Psoriasis: A clinical case study. *Journal of Ayurveda and integrative medicine*, 12(1), 172-177.
47. Bharati, P. L., Agrawal, P., & Prakash, O. (2019). A case study on the management of dry gangrene by Kaishore Guggulu, Sanjivani Vati and Dashanga Lepa. *AYU (An International Quarterly Journal of Research in Ayurveda)*, 40(1), 48-52.
48. Kataria, D., & Singh, G. (2024). Health benefits of ghee: Review of Ayurveda and modern science perspectives. *Journal of Ayurveda and integrative medicine*, 15(1), 100819.
49. Chatterjee, A., Jayaprakasan, M., Chakrabarty, A. K., Lakkaniga, N. R., Bhatt, B. N., Banerjee, D., ... & Dubey, S. K. (2024). Comprehensive insights into rheumatoid arthritis: Pathophysiology, current therapies and herbal alternatives for effective disease management. *Phytotherapy Research*, 38(6), 2764-2799.
50. Gupta RD. Gugulipid: Pro-lipaemic effect. *J Assoc Physicians India* 1990; 38: 598.
51. . Kay MA. Healing with plants in the American and Mexican west. The University of Arizona Press, Tuscon, 1996. 221-4 p.
52. Palombo EA. Phytochemicals from traditional Medicinal plants used in treatment of diarrhea: Mode of action and effect in intestinal functions. *Phytother Res* 2006; 20: 717-24.
53. Francis JA, Raja SN, Nair MG. Bioactive Terpenoids and guggulosteroids from *Commiphora Mukul* gum resin of potential anti-inflammatory Interest. *Chem Biodivers* 2004; 1: 1842-53.
54. Ulbricht C, Basch E, Szapary P, Hammer Ness P, Axentsev S, Boon H, Kroll D, Garraway L, Vora M, Woods J. Guggul for hyperlipidemia: A review by the Natural Standard Research Collaboration. *Complement Ther Med*. 2005; 13(4): 279-90.
55. Hess, B.R. 2002. Guggul (*Commiphora Mukul*). Internet address: <http://qualitycounts.com/fpguggul.html>. Last accessed on December 26, 2012.

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